

Short Introduction to Standard and NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic

(review paper)

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Abstract: The definitions of Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set (SVNS), Interval-Valued Neutrosophic Set (IVNS), Subset-Valued Neutrosophic Set (SVNS), and respectively NonStandard Neutrosophic Set [Single-Valued (NoS SVNS), Interval-Valued (NoS IVNS), and Subset-Valued (NoS SVNS)], are recalled together with their operators. Similarly for Standard and NonStandard Neutrosophic Logic.

1. Introduction

The neutrosophic set was introduced in 1995 by F. Smarandache as extension of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set. The first publications were in 1998-2005 [25, 26].

2. Standard Neutrosophic Set and Logic

Let \mathcal{U} be a universe of discourse, and \mathcal{S} a non-empty subset of \mathcal{U} . Let $t(x), i(x), f(x)$ be the degrees of truth (membership), indeterminacy, and falsehood (nonmembership) respectively of the generic element x with respect to the set \mathcal{S} .

Let $\mathcal{S} = \{x_{(t(x), i(x), f(x))}, \text{ for } x \in \mathcal{U}\}$.

2.1 Definition of Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set (SVNS)

\mathcal{S} is a Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set if:

$$t(x), i(x), f(x): \mathcal{S} \rightarrow [0,1]$$

(or $t(x), i(x), f(x)$ are single numbers in $[0, 1]$) such that:

$$0 \leq t(x) + i(x) + f(x) \leq 3$$

2.2 Definition of Interval-Valued Neutrosophic Set (IVNS)

\mathcal{S} is an Interval-Valued Neutrosophic Set if:

$$t(x), i(x), f(x): \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}([0,1])$$

where $\mathcal{P}([0,1])$ is the powerset of $[0, 1]$, and $t(x), i(x), f(x)$ are intervals included in $[0, 1]$ such that:

$$0 \leq \inf(t(x)) + \inf(i(x)) + \inf(f(x)) \leq \sup(t(x)) + \sup(i(x)) + \sup(f(x)) \leq 3$$

2.3 Definition of Subset-Valued Neutrosophic Set (SVNS)

\mathcal{S} is a Subset-Valued Neutrosophic Set if:

$$t(x), i(x), f(x): \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}([0,1])$$

and $t(x), i(x), f(x)$ are subsets included in $[0, 1]$ such that:

$$0 \leq \inf(t(x)) + \inf(i(x)) + \inf(f(x)) \leq \sup(t(x)) + \sup(i(x)) + \sup(f(x)) \leq 3$$

3. Necessity to Introduce the NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic

In order to make distinction between Relative Truth (truth in at least one world, according to Leibniz) and Absolute Truth (truth in all possible worlds, again according to Leibniz), we considered the NonStandard Analysis:

$t(x) = 1$, meaning relative truth (membership),

and $t(x) = 1^+$, meaning absolute truth (membership).

Similarly, for Relative Indeterminacy and Absolute Indeterminacy respectively:

$i(x) = 1$, for relative indeterminacy,

and $i(x) = 1^+$, for absolute indeterminacy.

And for Relative Falsehood (NonMembership), and Absolute Falsehood (NonMembership):

$f(x) = 1$, for relative falsehood (nonmembership),

and $f(x) = 1^+$, for absolute falsehood (nonmembership).

4. Introduction to NonStandard Analysis

Abraham Robinson in 1960s has developed the non-standard analysis [15, 16, 27, 28], by rigorously defining the infinitesimals and infinite numbers.

An *infinitesimal number* (ε) is a number ε such that its absolute value $|\varepsilon| < \frac{1}{n}$, for any non-null positive integer n . An infinitesimal is close to zero, and so small that it cannot be measured.

The infinitesimal is a number smaller, in absolute value, than anything positive nonzero. Infinitesimals are used in calculus, but interpreted as tiny real numbers.

An *infinite number* (ω) is a number greater than anything:

$$1 + 1 + 1 + \dots + 1 \text{ (for any finite number terms).}$$

The infinities are reciprocals of infinitesimals.

The set of *hyperreals* (*non-standard reals*), denoted as R^* , is the extension of set of the real numbers, denoted as R , and it comprises the infinitesimals and the infinities, that may be represented on the *hyperreal number line*

$$\frac{1}{\varepsilon} = \omega$$

The set of hyperreals satisfies the *transfer principle*, which states that the statements of first order in R are valid in R^* as well [according to the classical NonStandard Analysis].

A *monad* (*halo*) of an element $a \in R^*$, denoted by $\mu(a)$, is a subset of numbers infinitesimally close to a .

Let's denote by R_+^* the set of positive nonzero hyperreal numbers.

Left Monad and Right Monad were defined as follows:

Left Monad {that we denote, for simplicity, by (^-a) }, is defined as:

$$\mu(^-a) = (^-a) = \{a - x, x \in R_+^* | x \text{ is infinitesimal}\}$$

Right Monad {that we denote, for simplicity, by (a^+) }, is defined as:

$$\mu(a^+) = (a^+) = \{a + x, x \in R_+^* | x \text{ is infinitesimal}\}$$

5. Extensions of NonStandard Analysis

In 1998, Smarandache [25] introduced the Pierced Binad.

5.1. **Pierced Binad** {that we denote, for simplicity, by $(^-a^+)$ } is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(^-a^+) &= (^-a^+) = \\ &= \{a - x, x \in R_+^* | x \text{ is a positive infinitesimal}\} \cup \{a + x, x \in R_+^* | x \text{ is a positive infinitesimal}\} \\ &= \{a - x, x \in R^* | x \text{ is a positive or negative infinitesimal}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Later on, in 2019, Smarandache [23] also introduced the Left Monad Closed to the Right, The Right Monad closed to the Left, and the Unpierced Binad (all defined as below) in order to have the Nonstandard Real Monad/Binad Set closed under arithmetic operations.

5.2. Left Monad Closed to the Right

$$\begin{aligned} \mu\left(\begin{smallmatrix} -0 \\ a \end{smallmatrix}\right) &= \left(\begin{smallmatrix} -0 \\ a \end{smallmatrix}\right) = \{a - x | x = 0, \text{ or } x \in R_+^*, \text{ and } x \text{ is infinitesimal}\} \\ &= \mu(^-a) \cup \{a\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{By notation, } \mu\left(\begin{smallmatrix} 0 \\ a \end{smallmatrix}\right) = \left(\begin{smallmatrix} 0 \\ a \end{smallmatrix}\right) = \overset{0}{a} = a.$$

And by $x = \overset{-0}{a}$ we understand the hyperreal $x = a - \varepsilon$, or $x = a$, where ε is a positive infinitesimal. So, x is not clearly known, $x \in \{a - \varepsilon, a\}$.

5.3. Right Monad Closed to the Left

$$\begin{aligned} \mu\left(\begin{smallmatrix} 0+ \\ a \end{smallmatrix}\right) &= \left(\begin{smallmatrix} 0+ \\ a \end{smallmatrix}\right) = \{a + x | x = 0, \text{ or } x \in R_+^*, \text{ and } x \text{ is infinitesimal}\} \\ &= \mu(a^+) \cup \{a\} \end{aligned}$$

And by $x = \overset{0+}{a}$ we understand the hyperreal $x = a + \varepsilon$, or $x = a$, where ε is a positive infinitesimal. So, x is not clearly known, $x \in \{a, a + \varepsilon\}$.

5.4. Unpierced Binad

$$\begin{aligned}\mu\left(\begin{matrix} -0+ \\ a \end{matrix}\right) &= \left(\begin{matrix} -0+ \\ a \end{matrix}\right) = \{a + x \mid x = 0, \text{ or } x \in R^*, \text{ and } x \text{ is positive or negative infinitesimal}\} \\ &= \mu(-a) \cup (a^+) \cup \{a\} = (-a) \cup (a^+) \cup \{a\}\end{aligned}$$

And by $x = \begin{matrix} -0+ \\ a \end{matrix}$ we understand the *hyperreal* $x = a - \varepsilon$, or $x = a$, or $x = a + \varepsilon$, where ε is a positive infinitesimal. So, x is not clearly known, $x \in \{a - \varepsilon, a, a + \varepsilon\}$.

The left monad, left monad closed to the right, right monad, right monad closed to the left, the pierced binad, and the unpierced binad are subsets of R^* , while the above hyperreals are numbers from R^* .

6. NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic

Let \mathcal{U} be a universe of discourse, and \mathcal{S} a non-empty subset of \mathcal{U} .

Let $\mathcal{S} = \{x_{(t(x), i(x), f(x))}, \text{ for } x \in \mathcal{U}\}$.

6.1 Definition of Single-Valued NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic

\mathcal{S} is an Single-Valued NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic, if:

$$t(x), i(x), f(x): \mathcal{S} \rightarrow]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$$

where $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ is the nonstandard unit interval, which is a set that contains, besides the ordinary real numbers between 0 and 1, also:

Left Monads, Right Monads;

As well as the newly introduced by Smarandache [23, 25] in 1998-2019:

Left Monads closed to the Right,

Right Monads closed to the Left,

Pierced Binads,

and Unpierced Binads.

Of course, $[0, 1] \subset]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$.

Also,

$$-0 \leq \inf(t(x)) + \inf(i(x)) + \inf(f(x)) \leq \sup(t(x)) + \sup(i(x)) + \sup(f(x)) \leq 3^+$$

6.2 Definition of Interval-Valued NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic

\mathcal{S} is an Interval-Valued NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic, if:

$$t(x), i(x), f(x): \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(]^{-0}, 1^+[)$$

where $\mathcal{P}(]^{-0}, 1^+[)$ is the powerset of all standard and nonstandard subset of $]^{-0}, 1^+[$

with $t(x), i(x), f(x)$ being nonstandard intervals of the form:

$$]_{a'}^* b^* [$$

where $0 \leq a \leq b \leq 1$, and $\# a < \# b$,

where $a \in \{a, a, a, a, a, a, a, a\}$

similarly $b \in \{b, b, b, b, b, b, b, b\}$.

6.3 Definition of Subset-Valued NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic

\mathcal{S} is a Subset-Valued NonStandard Neutrosophic Set and Logic, if:

$$t(x), i(x), f(x): \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(]^{-0}, 1^+[)$$

with $t(x), i(x), f(x)$ being nonstandard subsets of the nonstandard interval $]^{-0}, 1^+[$.

7. Standard and NonStandard Neutrosophic Operators

Firstly we need to recall the t-norm and t-conorm from the fuzzy set and logic:

7.1. A *t-norm* [29] is a function $t: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that satisfies the following properties:

- Commutativity: $t(a, b) = t(b, a)$
- Monotonicity: $t(a, b) \leq t(c, d)$ if $a \leq c$ and $b \leq d$
- Associativity: $t(a, t(b, c)) = t(t(a, b), c)$
- The number 1 acts as identity element: $t(a, 1) = a$

A common notation in fuzzy set and logic is $t(a, b) = a \wedge_{\mathbb{F}} b$, meaning intersection respectively conjunction.

A *t-conorm* [29] is a function $\perp: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that satisfies the following properties:

- Commutativity: $\perp(a, b) = \perp(b, a)$
- Monotonicity: $\perp(a, b) \leq \perp(c, d)$ if $a \leq c$ and $b \leq d$
- Associativity: $\perp(a, \perp(b, c)) = \perp(\perp(a, b), c)$
- Identity element: $\perp(a, 0) = a$

A common notation in fuzzy set and logic is $t(a, b) = a \vee_F b$, meaning union respectively disjunction.

All the above types of Neutrosophic Standard and NonStandard Operators are based on the fuzzy t-norm (\wedge_F) and fuzzy t-conorm (\vee_F).

Let $x(T, I, F)$

7.2. Neutrosophic Standard and NonStandard Intersection/Conjunction (\wedge_N)

$$x(T_1, I_1, F_1) \wedge_N x(T_2, I_2, F_2) = x(T_1 \wedge_F T_2, I_1 \vee_F I_2, F_1 \vee_F F_2)$$

7.3. Neutrosophic Standard and NonStandard Union/Disjunction (\vee_N)

$$x(T_1, I_1, F_1) \vee_N x(T_2, I_2, F_2) = x(T_1 \vee_F T_2, I_1 \wedge_F I_2, F_1 \wedge_F F_2)$$

7.4. Neutrosophic Standard and NonStandard Complement/Negation (\neg_N)

$$\neg_N x(T, I, F) = \bar{x}(F, 1 - I, T)$$

7.5. Neutrosophic Standard and NonStandard Implication (\rightarrow_N)

$$A_1(T_1, I_1, F_1) \rightarrow_N A_2(T_2, I_2, F_2)$$

is neutrosophically equivalent with

$$\neg_N A_1(T_1, I_1, F_1) \vee_N A_2(T_2, I_2, F_2)$$

7.6. Neutrosophic Standard and NonStandard Equivalence (\leftrightarrow_N)

$$A_1(T_1, I_1, F_1) \leftrightarrow_N A_2(T_2, I_2, F_2)$$

is neutrosophically equivalent with

$$A_1(T_1, I_1, F_1) \rightarrow_N A_2(T_2, I_2, F_2) \text{ and } A_2(T_2, I_2, F_2) \rightarrow_N A_1(T_1, I_1, F_1).$$

Conclusion

In this paper we reviewed the various types of standard and nonstandard neutrosophic sets and logics, used for about three decades of scientific research and applications.

With the help of the fuzzy t-norm and fuzzy t-conorm we recalled the definitions of the neutrosophic standard and nonstandard operators.

References

- [1] Imamura, Takuma (2018). On the Definition of Neutrosophic Logic. arXiv:1811.02961 [Submitted on 7 Nov 2018 (v1), last revised 17 Aug 2022 (v2)]. Cornell University, USA. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1811.02961>
- [2] Xindong Peng and Jingguo Dai (2018). A bibliometric analysis of neutrosophic set: two decades review from 1998 to 2017. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, Springer, 18 August 2018; <http://fs.unm.edu/BibliometricNeutrosophy.pdf>
- [3] Smarandache, Florentin (2013). n-Valued Refined Neutrosophic Logic and Its Applications in Physics. *Progress in Physics* 4, 143-146. UNM website: <http://fs.unm.edu/n-ValuedNeutrosophicLogic-PiP.pdf>
- [4] Smarandache, Florentin (2002). Neutrosophy, A New Branch of Philosophy. *Multiple Valued Logic / An International Journal* 8(3), 297-384
- [5] Smarandache, Florentin (1998). Neutrosophy. Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic. ProQuest Information & Learning, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA. UNM website: <http://fs.unm.edu/eBook-Neutrosophics6.pdf>
- [6] Smarandache, Florentin (2002). A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. *Multiple Valued Logic / An International Journal* 8(3), 385-438. {The whole issue of this journal is dedicated to Neutrosophy and Neutrosophic Logic.}
- [7] Smarandache, Florentin (2003). Definition of neutrosophic logic - a generalization of the intuitionistic fuzzy logic. Proceedings of the 3rd Conference of the European Society for Fuzzy Logic and Technology, 2003, pp. 141-146
- [8] Smarandache, Florentin (2016). Neutrosophic Overset, Neutrosophic Underset, and Neutrosophic Offset. Similarly for Neutrosophic Over-/Under-/Off- Logic, Probability, and Statistics, Pons, Bruxelles, Belgium. UNM Digital Repository: https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/math_fsp/26/

- [9] Ashbacher, Charles (2002). Section: „Logical Connectives in Neutrosophic Logic”, pp. 59-72 in his book „Introduction to Neutrosophic Logic”, ProQuest Information & Learning, Ann Arbor. <http://fs.unm.edu/IntroNeutLogic.pdf>
- [10] Riviuccio, Umberto (2008). Neutrosophic logics: Prospects and Problems. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 159(14), 1860-1868.
- [11] Smarandache, Florentin (2017). Plithogeny, Plithogenic Set, Logic, Probability, and Statistics, Pons Publishing House, Brussels, Belgium, 141 p., 2017; arXiv.org (Cornell University), Computer Science - Artificial Intelligence, 03Bxx: <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1808/1808.03948.pdf>
- [12] Nguyen Xuan Thao; Smarandache, Florentin (2016). (I, T)-Standard neutrosophic rough set and its topologies properties. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 14, 65-70. https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/nss_journal/vol14/iss1/11/
- [13] Nguyen Xuan Thao; Bui Cong Cuong; Smarandache, Florentin (2016). Rough Standard Neutrosophic Sets: An Application on Standard Neutrosophic Information Systems. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 14, 80-92. <http://fs.unm.edu/NSS/RoughStandardNeutrosophicSets.pdf>
- [14] Bui Cong Cuong; Pham Hong Phong; Smarandache, Florentin (2016). Standard Neutrosophic Soft Theory - Some First Results. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 12, 80-91. <http://fs.unm.edu/NSS/StandardNeutrosophicSoftTheory.pdf>
- [15] Insall, Matt and Weisstein, Eric W. "Nonstandard Analysis." From MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/NonstandardAnalysis.html>
- [16] Insall, Matt. "Transfer Principle." From *MathWorld* - A Wolfram Web Resource, created by Eric W. Weisstein. <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/TransferPrinciple.html>
- [17] Smarandache, Florentin (2017). Applications of Neutrosophic Sets in Image Identification, Medical Diagnosis, Fingerprints and Face Recognition and Neutrosophic Overset/Underset/Offset. COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Abbottabad, Pakistan, December 26th, 2017.
- [18] Smarandache, Florentin (2016). Interval-Valued Neutrosophic Oversets, Neutrosophic Undersets, and Neutrosophic Offsets. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations* 5(54), 1-4.
- [19] Smarandache, Florentin (2016). Operators on Single-Valued Neutrosophic Oversets, Neutrosophic Undersets, and Neutrosophic Offsets. *Journal of Mathematics and Informatics* 5, 63-67.
- [20] Smarandache, Florentin (2018). About Nonstandard Neutrosophic Logic (Answers to Imamura Note *On the Definition of Neutrosophic Logic*), 16 p., Cornell University, New York City, USA. {Submitted on 24 Nov 2018 (version 1), last revised 13 Feb 2019 (version 2)}. Abstract: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1812.02534v2>. Full paper:

<https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1812/1812.02534.pdf>. UNM Website:
<https://fs.unm.edu/neut/AboutNonstandardNeutrosophicLogic.pdf>

[21] Imamura, Takuma (2022). On the Definition of Neutrosophic Logic. *Journal of Japan Society for Fuzzy Theory and Intelligent Informatics* 34(3):669–672.

https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/jsoft/34/3/34_669/article/-char/ja/

[22] Imamura, Takuma (2022). Emails to the Author, August 2022.

[23] Smarandache, Florentin (2019). Extended Nonstandard Neutrosophic Logic, Set, and Probability based on Extended Nonstandard Analysis. *Symmetry* 2019, 11, 515. DOI: 10.3390/sym11040515. Also in arXiv:1903.04558, Cornell University,

<https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1903/1903.04558.pdf>

[24] Smarandache, Florentin (2019). Advances of Standard and Nonstandard Neutrosophic Theories. Pons, Brussels, Belgium, 307 p. UNM Digital Repository:

https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/math_fsp/190/

[25] Smarandache, Florentin (1998 - 2007). A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability and Statistics. 6th edition. InfoLearnQuest, USA. UNM Digital Repository:

https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/math_fsp/163/

[26] Smarandache, F., Neutrosophic Set is a Generalization of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set, Inconsistent Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set (Picture Fuzzy Set, Ternary Fuzzy Set), Pythagorean Fuzzy Set (Atanassov's Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set of second type), q-Rung Orthopair Fuzzy Set, Spherical Fuzzy Set, and n-HyperSpherical Fuzzy Set, while Neutrosophication is a Generalization of Regret Theory, Grey System Theory, and Three-Ways Decision (revisited), *Journal of New Theory* 29 (2019) 01-35; arXiv, Cornell University, New York City, NY, USA, pp. 1-50, 17-29 November 2019, <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1911/1911.07333.pdf>; University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, USA, Digital Repository, pp. 1-50, https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/math_fsp/21.

[27] Robinson, Abraham (1996) [1966], Non-standard analysis. Princeton Landmarks in Mathematics. 2nd edition, Princeton University Press, USA.

[28] Robinson, Abraham (1963). Introduction to model theory and to the metamathematics of algebra. Amsterdam: North-Holland.

[29] Hájek, Petr (1998), Metamathematics of Fuzzy Logic. Dordrecht: Kluwer. ISBN 0-7923-5238-6.

Received: Aug 15, 2024. Accepted: Nov 9, 2024